

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

D3.4. Matching Interface design

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Deliverable 3.4

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I. Executive summary

This document complements the release of the D3.4 - Matching Interface design deliverable, which is the release of the interface itself as a service for the VERA community due in March 2023. The aim of this service is to allow VERA users to more easily find potential collaborators for their project and invite them to be part of it.

The tool is designed to connect users based on their interests and skills. With this tool, VERA users will be suggested about potential collaborators to invite as members of a project. This tool is expected to enhance the platform's ability to facilitate collaboration and support SSH citizen science communities in building a successful team for their project.

The VERA matchmaking service can be seen as a complementary tool to the Fundit integration that aims at suggesting funding opportunities for projects (developed under WP4 - Funding Advocacy) and represents a functionality that enhances the project features to support its evolution and growth.

Similar to other functionalities developed so far, the matching service has been foreseen as an evolving tool. In this first stage of release, a project administrator can activate the functionality to see a list of recommended users and quickly invite them to the project.

In particular, the matchmaking system will use the following criteria as basic conditions:

- Users have a public profile
- Users have selected “open to collaboration” in their profile settings
- Users are not already part of the team of the project

As second level conditions:

- VERA matchmaking active (at project level)
- Language spoken (at project and users level)
- At least 1 academic subject in common (at project and users level)

The list of suggested users will be regularly refreshed and ordered by date of sign up.

As a further enhancement of this matchmaking tool, being VERA one of the OPERAS services¹, it will be also integrated with the GoTriple² platform - a multilingual discovery platform for the Social Sciences and Humanities developed under the EU funded project TRIPLE - allowing users to receive suggested profiles among the public SSH related profiles registered on GoTriple and with the status “open to collaboration”.

A further future enhancement of the matchmaking will be based on semantic technologies to match projects and users based on the meaning of their descriptions rather than simply matching keywords.

¹ Cfr. Deliverable 3.2 VERA Core Design and Development (pp 16-20)

<https://zenodo.org/record/5889298#.ZCHp2exBzFo>

² <https://gotriple.eu/>

I. Structure of the document

This document is structured in III sections:

- Section I: Executive summary
- Section II: Description of the Matchmaking tool user journey
- Section III: Conclusions

II. VERA Matching tool user journey

In this section we explain in detail the flow of matchmaking, providing the screenshots of the main elements of this new feature.

In the project section, under the “Team” tab there will be the possibility of accessing a list of recommended users by activating a specific *toggle* under the “Matchmaking” tab. The Cambridge Dictionary defines the toggle as follows: a key or button on a computer that is pressed to turn a feature on and then off. Select the function you require by pointing to the toggle (= image of a button on the screen) with the mouse and then clicking.

Figure 1 - Matchmaking tab and toggles

Once the toggle is switched on, a list of suggested users will be displayed, as shown in the following screenshot. The user will be able to view the detailed profiles (via the “View profile” link) and if a suitable user is identified, to invite them to be part of the team via the “Invite to team” function.

Figure 2 - List of recommended users once VERA matchmaking toggle is activated

By clicking on “Invite to team” a pop up banner will appear that will allow to select a proposed role for the team member and specific access rights to the project.

Figure 3 - Invitation popup interface (1/2)

By clicking on the “Continue” button users can then personalise the invitation with a message and send it.

Figure 4 - Invitation popup interface (2/2)

Once this process is complete, a confirmation message will appear.

Figure 5 - Confirmation message once invitation is complete

The invited user will then appear under the “Team management” list with a pending status until they accept or decline the invitation.

vera VERA Hub Browse projects Discover people Find funding [+ Create project](#) **M** Massimiliano

A Criminological Study on Businesses in Rome Public

[Setup](#) **Team management** Matchmaking

Team overview [+ Invite new members](#)

Manage the team members on your project

Name	Email	Role	Access	Status
Massimiliano Spinosa	massispinosa@gmail.com	Data Analyst	Member	Pending
Max Weber	Maximw@yahoo.com	Project manager	Admin	Joined
John Smith	tomjones@gmail.com	Public relations	Admin	Joined
Esther Howard	howard32457@gmail.com	General contributor	Admin	Pending

Figure 5 - Team overview

III. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the interface and the user journey designed to support matchmaking within VERA.

As the VERA platform has been designed with the purpose of facilitating collaboration, the possibility of matching users to projects is a functionality that will render finding new research partners, especially from different backgrounds, a much more streamlined process and adds unique value to the VERA platform. As far as we are aware, from the benchmark analysis and netnography that has been carried out³, no other platform on the market provides this type of facilitated research partner discovery for SSH practitioners.

In the overall activities of WP3, which is devoted to the development of the VERA platform, this advanced functionality represents a key step forward towards the final release of VERA at the end of the COESO project.

The matching tool itself is planned to evolve in the next few months supporting the suggestions of possible collaborators from the GoTriple platform and to support a matchmaking based on semantic technologies.

³ Cfr. Deliverable 3.1 User Experience / User Interface design (pp 8-11)
<https://zenodo.org/record/6523503#.ZCHrjOxBzFo>